

P: ISSN No. 2231-0045
E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438

VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Periodic Research

Equitable Employment Laws Vis-A-Vis Lgbtqia Protection from Discrimination at Workplace in India

Paper Id : 20448 Submission Date : 2025-05-04 Acceptance Date : 2025-05-21 Publication Date : 2025-05-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16473782

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/researchtimes.php#8>

Ritu Kumari

Advocate
Law
Baran District Court
Rajasthan, India

Abstract

This paper aims to delve into the specific factors that have contributed to continued disparity faced by the LGBT community (hereinafter referred to as 'The Community') in India within employment sector. Despite the legal recognition and protections given to them, it is all important to find out the underlying attitude that continues to hinder their full participation which can lead to an advance workforce. The study aims to delve deeper into these issues and provide a comprehensive analysis of challenges and hurdles that gives the light upon the phenomenon.

The author examines and points out that the new labour code lacks specific anti-discrimination laws for the community. It further stated that the scope of legislation related in context of preventing sexual harassment whereas this contrasts the scope of with prior Indian legal precedents that addresses sexual harassment without specifying gender. The study also measures the LGBT community within military legislation, potentially subjecting individuals to serious offenses based on their identification.

Keywords Employment Rights, Discrimination Based on Sexuality, Personal Autonomy, LGBTQIA and Anti-Discrimination Policy in Employment.

Introduction The author highlights the ongoing challenges faced by the community despite of the legal protection they have received, drawing upon the research from the reputable international organization. At last, the author examines the legislation and the policy of the foreign nation that have implemented mandatory anti-discrimination measures to safeguard the well-being of the community workers. The research also pointed out the anti-discrimination policies in Indian organization and explains the dire need for the same to get legalised.

Objective of study

1. To identify the public policy and laws that aims abolishing gender discrimination at workplace in India, specifically discrimination based on traits of gender i.e., sexuality.
2. To promote Inclusion and Eliminate of LGBTQIA discrimination and assessing its Positive impact on Company's Growth.

Research Question:

1. Whether citizens of India have laws to their recourse which deals with abolition of discrimination at workplace based on gender and sexuality?
2. Whether promotion of inclusive policies in employment sector for LGBTQIA community leads positive impact on the overall growth of an organization?

Review of Literature

Bostock v. Clayton County (US Supreme Court)[1]

The observations of this landmark judgement by the US Supreme Court deals with interpretation of the terms "Sex" in Title VII of the Civil Rights Act of 1964. The enactment prohibits any kind of discrimination on the ground of sex, but the sex means only binary genders or does it include sexuality as well, was the issue of main contention in this case. The reasoning given in the majority judgment states that discrimination based on sexuality ultimately leads to the employer discriminating on the ground of sex,

as if two employees, one being male and another being female, both have same sexual preference, and if only male employee is discriminated, then it is ultimately because of discrimination based on sex. And, it has also been stated that sexuality is a part of sex, and it varies from person to person and is a matter of personal preference, so discrimination on that ground is not just. The dissenting judgement rejects the majority judgement on the ground of strict separation of powers, i.e., Judiciary is expected to interpret the law as what it is, and not how it ought to be. The majority judgement has also stated that the employer will be liable for the discrimination only if he does it with the intention to discriminate on the basis of sex, but how to ascertain and establish that intention haven't been discussed, leaving a gap for the employers to escape the liability by citing some ancillary ground for discrimination while actually discriminating on the ground of sex/sexuality.

Chinder Pal Singh v. The Chief Secretary and Ors. 2023/RJP/011257[2]

The above case is one of the most important and the leading case which concerns about the recognition of gender identity, particularly for transgender individuals in India with reference to availing the service of employment. The court was delved upon with different principle and rules. The counsel in this case started with pointing out Rig Veda which states as per the Hindu mythology there are three genders identifies male (purush), female (prakriti) and tritya prakriti.

The recognition of third gender is a part of the ancient era. "Article 14 of the Indian Constitution" that is the equal protection of law for every person was also included to interpret the transgender persons. The court recognized that transgender individuals who do not conform to traditional male or female categories are entitled to legal protection in various aspects of life including employment, healthcare and education. Furthermore, the Article 21 of "Indian Constitution" court emphasized that the transgender are not limited to the binary gender. Lastly, the legislation given for transgender that is the "Transgender Person (Protection of Rights), Act, 2019" and the Act recognized the "Trans-person" and classifies the term trans-woman and trans-man.

In the case of **National Legal Service Authority v. Union of India[3]**, Supreme Court upheld Transgender persons right to decide the self-identified gender.

In the present case it was concluded by the court that the petitioner who has gone through the sex reassignment surgery to transition from female to male should be recognized as male and as a result he was entitled to have his name corrected in the service record.

This being a very crucial step taken in India that is the recognition of self-identified gender but this judgment lacks in proper identification of history that is the interpretation of Yog Karta principle which were discussed in the "Application of International Human Rights Law" which was based on sexual orientation and gender identity as well as interpreted in the NALSA Judgment which states that:

"There should be no eligibility criteria, such as medical or psychological interventions, a psycho-medical diagnosis, minimum or maximum age, economic status, health, marital or parental status, or any other third-party opinion, shall be a prerequisite to change one's name, legal sex or gender"

The term should be interpreted in partial manner because the medical criteria is something which is crucial in accordance with the legislation of transgender but the other criteria should be considered.

Nangai v. The Superintendent of Police, Karur District[4]

The High Court of Madras, in this was faced with an de novo issue of law related to legality of forced medical examination to and based on the results imposing a forced gender identity on the Petitioner. The single judge bench answered the issue condemning such acts as illegal and being against the right to life.

The important thing to be noticed is that this judgement is passed just after 2 days of the landmark NALSA Judgment. S. Nagamuthu, J should be appreciated for taking due cognizance of the landmark judgment on the rights of Transgenders. However, the observation of S. Nagamuthu, J is not practically viable as the particular observation of not counting woman converting to a man or a woman having certain external or internal characteristics of a man as a transgender is not what the Supreme court could intend or

afford to confer a status of law, as doing so would be classifying the community and would be a grave injustice for the section of the transgender who are born as female.

The important thing to be noticed is that the Justice has tried to research and reach to a conclusion that the law has not delved in establishing who are male and who are females in the technical sense. We still don't have a law which defines who can be identified as males, females and third gender leading to the concept of gender fluidity as per the whims and fancies under the garb of one's personal autonomy.

V. Vasanta Mogli v. State of Telangana[5]

The judgement dwells upon the issue of privacy and acceptance faced by the Transgenders due to some draconian laws prevailing in the society. The Petition is the clubbed form of Public Interest Litigations the concerns of whom were inter-related. The first PIL dwells the constitutional validity of draconian penal laws dealing with offences committed by transgenders, and ultimately stereotyping third genders as criminals. The second PIL deals with the claim for substantive equality for the transgenders through reservation considering them to be SEBC. The third PIL was with respect to the Transgenders unable to avail the benefit of schemes and Yojnas by the government during the period of lock, because of not having any ration cards or the required identity proofs, because the form to be filled didn't had the gender option for third genders.

The judgment has tried whip the government to carry its responsibilities towards the transgenders who also have the right to welfare schemes of the Unions and states. However, even after the landmark judgements like that of NALSA in 2013, the situation has not changed much as the suggestions of the Supreme Court has not been even tried to be implemented in its full force. The Transgenders still face discrimination in matters related to equitable distribution of national resources and opportunities in public employment through the Reservation quota which they deserve for upliftment of the community. Irrespective of whether being a private sector or public sector, the third gender face disparity and discrimination during recruitment as well as at the workplace, which is a leading cause of their unstable source and rate of income. And, in this judgement, although the government is asked to do all that is prayed in the three PILs, however, no specific mechanism is laid down leading the ratio decidendi have weightage similar to obiter dicta of the court.

Research Articles/Papers/Journals

Trans Equality in India: Affirmation of the Right to Self-Determination of Gender[6]

The research articles deal with a very important concern which needs to be addressed before the transgenders could be granted reservation and access to beneficiary schemes in employment and education sector i.e., whether medical examination should be mandated for identification of gender of people in order to avoid the welfare legislations to be misused by the people who are non-transgenders. The author should be appreciated for bringing such an important issue into light.

However, the author has failed to analyse the Transgender protection Act, and has ended up conferring its provisions in a wrong manner, deviating from the object of the Act. Section 7 of the Act doesn't require the medical certificate to prove one's inherent gender which oneself feels, but is talking about the gender after surgery. And, if a transgender goes under the knife to change their biological gender, there should not be a problem for them to produce the certificate, which they would've most probably received from the medical institution. The issue with this provision will only arise in case of an intersex person who, if wants to declare himself as man or woman, would require medical certificate, for which they have to do the surgery.

The medical model, have been clearly rejected by the author stating that, it fails to recognise all the variations in the transgenders people. The author fails to take a balanced approach considering the fact that if an absolute personal autonomy is given to everyone to decide their gender as per their own will, they may keep changing their gender as per their whims and fancies. And, therefore there is scope for some restricted and balanced approach when it comes to personal autonomy model and medical recognition model, so that both can be implemented harmoniously.

The Economic Cost of Stigma and the Exclusion of Lgbt People: A Case Study of India[7]

This paper discusses apart from social hindrances for the LGBT (hereinafter referred to as "the community") people in India there is a need to know that how much the equality for the community people is important as inclusion of the community is important for the economic-development issue. This paper has pointed out regarding unemployment of the community basically the exclusion of lead to developmental issue in the country and this

P: ISSN No. 2231-0045
E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438

VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Periodic Research

paper has specifically discussed upon the structure of the community employment in India.

This paper has provided some of the factors which says exclusion of LGBT can be potentially costly to the economy and which are as follows:

1. Lower Productivity and Output because of employment discrimination which lead to lower supply of labors;
2. Less investment in human capital which leads to lower returns to education because there was discrimination at educational institutes;
3. Social and health services required to address the effects of exclusion that might be better spent elsewhere.

This particular paper has mentioned "India is the country which does not allow precise cost because of LGBT exclusion" and this is most crucial issue because if a country is lagging behind economically because of one section people discriminated it can affect one of the most important factors of economy that is "Labor".

LGBT Inequality in the Federal Workforce: Intersectional Processes, Organizational Contexts, and Turnover Consideration [8]

The article abovementioned discusses about the discrimination of workers belonging to LGBT community basically and how the difference is created between LGBT and Non-LGBT in the US workforce in their day-to-day work life. This is a context which relates to the status of workers belonging to LGBT community that how does it lead to inequalities among workers in the organisation. The paper has brought up the concept of "Status inequality theory" because of the negative beliefs that establish a norm upon the naturalness about the "transgender and homosexual" there is also an assumption about LGBT people that they this community is a bit lethargic and incompetent to work and they are someone who are affecting the moral beliefs. This paper states that because of the cultural beliefs the LGBT community are provided with fewer resources and there is less preference given to them in the sense of training, supervision and also there is bias among the social interaction among LGBT and Non-LGBT. This is something which will lead to the person belonging to this community will hide their status and if this is revealed this disclosure because of the heterosexual comments from the colleagues of the company and this will lead to discrimination towards the LGBT even after the status given to them because it is invisible towards the co-workers who are working in the organisation.

It is stated an organisation loses their effectiveness due to turnover of the negative employees in an organisation as it was shown by the scholars that there is a clear linkage of employee satisfaction and worker productivity. This can lead to decreased morale, decreased productivity and decreased efficiency. Additionally, it can lead to a decrease in overall customer satisfaction as the turnover of the company is low.

Methodology This research paper involves a methodology of doctrinal research with analysis of various topic for understanding the concept of International Investment. The author has used several primary and secondary analytical material to construct qualitative research in the form of solution to the issues framed with respect to Employment Law with regards to LGBTQIA community.

Analysis

Laws and Grounds for prohibition of discrimination at workplace based on Gender and Sexuality

Employment in Manufacturing and Labour Sector:

Discrimination based on gender is not something new to anybody, and specifically, women have been considered as a vulnerable group when it comes to discrimination based on gender, to overcome which the legislators has enacted laws like Equal Remuneration Act 1976[9], POSH Act 2013[10], Maternity Benefit Act 1961[11], etc. And, it is a not a novice that these laws are specifically inclined towards women in the labour market. The term women have nowhere been technically defined anywhere and as per the NALSA judgment every human being have the personal autonomy to decide their gender which is felt inherently and is more a soul-based concept than biological.[12].

Now, as per the Transgender (Protection of Rights) Act, 2019[13] every man who considers himself as a female is entitled to be respected and identified as a woman. And, suppose the man undergoes a sex reassignment surgery (SRS) to get converted into a woman, so he'll be known as a trans-woman. That trans-women can by producing the medical certificate about the sex-reassignment surgery to the magistrate so designated for, can proclaim herself to be identified as a female. Now the issue is, whether that transgender who has got converted to a female through SRS, would also be entitled to

the protection prescribed under the laws as stated in the para supra for protection of women against discrimination in the labour and manufacturing sector.

The answer most probably will lie in the Transgender Act of 2019 itself as it is a special law. Section 3 of the Act in its clause (b) & (c) and Section 9 specifically provides for abolition of discrimination with transgenders in matters related to employment. Section 9 being inclusive in nature, tends to cover the matters related to employment like, remuneration, healthy workplace environment, just terms of employment agreement, etc apart from recruitment and promotion, as already specified.

In fact, the Act also prescribes under section 14 that, the government is bound to formulate welfare schemes for transgenders which will aim at welfare of the transgender community by providing them with the requisite training to enter the employment sector, and creating self-employment opportunities for them. Also, the definition of transgenders includes women who were biologically made; therefore, protection has to be sought under this act. However, we should not infer it with an absolute affirmation that, the trans-women are not allowed to seek remedy under the beneficial laws for women, as this would be denying them the right to proclaim their womanhood. It is pertinent to mention that, the new labour codes also don't have any special or specific provisions for the welfare of transgender communities, except for Occupational Safety, Health and Working Conditions Code, 2020 which speaks about facilities like toilet and hygiene at workplaces. When it comes to International Labour Organization, it has formed the Equal Remuneration Convention of 1951, which abstains from recognizing equality in pay for the third genders.[14]

Employment discrimination in the Defence sector:

Shifting our focus from the manufacturing market, it is pertinent to dwell upon the discrimination based on gender and sexuality in the Army sector of employment, which is the largest employment sector with 14,00,000 employees. The issue with the Army sector is that, it is not ready to accept homosexual acts as legal, and is considered as a conduct leading to a personnel unbecoming the or abandoning the character expected of him to exude while being a part of any three pillars of the Indian Army.[15] This can be observed from the few incidents and interviews of the respected personalities like Army Chief General Bipin Rawat and Major Navdeep Singh who conferred that homosexual act is indecent as per the code and discipline required to be in Army, and hence, personnel not only could be barred from being an officer of the Army, but could be punished as well under section 46 of the Army Act, 1950. And, the astonishing fact is that, these statements were made after section 377 was decriminalized in the landmark judgement of Navtej Singh Johar[16]. It should be kept in mind that, although defence sector is a separate area of employment for, and therefore, may not be used for social reforms. However, this is not an excuse to violate basic right to equality for LGBTQIA community.

Reservation and Welfare for Third Gender:

Till now we discussed about the plight of transgenders when it comes to recognizing them just as person who are citizens of India, however, as per the NALSA Judgement, they constitute a socially and educationally backward class of our society, hence, entitled to reservations. However, whether actually granting them with reservation is viable or not has not been discussed in the judgement. The Rights of Transgender Persons Bill, 2014[17] was the first bill introduced in the Rajya Sabha, which had a mention of reservation for them under the proposed section 21 and 22, in education institutions and public employment accounting to only 2 per cent of the total seats. The Bill, if would've been enacted would have made the government duty bound to provide incentives to the private establishers for constituting at least two percent of its workforce amongst the transgenders, within one year of the enactment (Section 23).

The government would also be liable to collect data from all over the nation regarding status of progress of transgenders in the employment sectors (Section 24). The government was very much reluctant in passing the bill as this would impose an extra burden on them with respect to already overburdening caste-based reservation system in India. Another argument that was put forth was that, the definition of transgenders under the Act was broad enough to encapsulate gender queers as well, and in such case all the people who doesn't identify themselves as cis-genders, even if socially and educationally advanced, would be entitled to reservation, which is not something what the substantive equality aims at.[18] Therefore, after a lot of amendments, the bill was passed in the year 2019 by both the houses and was brought into force from 10th January, 2020. Important thing to be noted about the 2019 Act is that, none of the welfare provisions as stated in the 2014 bill, and reiterated in para supra, which made the government duty bound to provide adequate opportunities to the transgenders have been included in the Act. The Act imposes the liability on the employers and the establishments for discrimination

against transgenders, but no punishment for such discrimination has been prescribed. Section 18 of the Act nowhere mentions punishment for establishments discriminating against transgenders. The 2014 Bill did prescribe punishment for the offences by establishments; however, the bill was silent on issue what would constitute an offence by establishments and employers.

The 2014 bill also provided for establishment of State and Central Commissions for protection and promotion of transgender rights with much wider powers and functions as compared to that of National Council for transgender in the 2019 Act. For example, the Act abstains from encapsulating Suo-moto powers to inquire into the incidents of violations, as well as interfere in the proceeding of any court, deal with such issues, with its due permission in the functions of the National Council under Section 17 of the 2019 Act.

Discrimination in Education Sector:

Now, let us shift our discussion to higher education system which is governed by UGC. The situation in this sector is not similar and inconsiderate towards the community. Under the University Grants Commission Sexual Harassment Regulations of the year 2016, regulation 3(1)(d) states that no form of sexual harassment should be tolerated in and by any HEI against any person, irrespective of gender or sexuality. The regulation specifically prescribes that although women, are generally the most vulnerable groups when it comes to sexual offence and harassment, it is in no manner restricted to only women, and even males, third genders or the students or employees exhibiting homosexuality are susceptible to these form of humiliation through violation of their privacy. This regulation is one of the firsts and a landmark recognition of the principle laid down in the judgements like that of NALSA for right to dignity of every person irrespective of his/her/their gender or sexuality.

Gender Neutrality for protection from Sexual Humiliation at Workplace:

Technically, only heterosexual females and lesbians can take recourse to the POSH Act for humiliation and harassment suffered at workplace. POSH Act was enacted to bring into force the spirit and principles conferred in the case of Vishakha v. State of Rajasthan, however 2013 Act fails to do so by limiting the scope of victims of sexual harassment only to women. For a long time after the enactment of the POSH Act, due to the stereotypical thinking of the society, it was only men who were considered as the perpetrators of sexual harassment. However, the tables have turned, and due to the judgements like that of Hiral P. Hasora v. Kusum Narottamdas (2016) 10 SCC 165, and Dr. Malbika Bhattacharjee v. ICC[19] (Calcutta HC, 2020), where it has been conferred that the kind and nature of offence prescribed under the POSH Act relates to dignity and integrity of an individual, which can be violated by a person of any gender or sexuality, therefore, the considering on males as the perpetrator would be unlawful and against equal protection of law for the victims of sexual harassment.

In the case of Hiral P. Hasora, it was conferred that restricting the meaning of perpetrator to only adult male persons will ultimately defeat the purpose of the Domestic Violence Act, 2005, and therefore should include every person irrespective of his/her/their gender. Through this judgement we can observe that through the tool of judicial interpretation, we even can expand a term which in its literal interpretation is absolutely restricted. The Bench in the hereinabove referred judgement has also conferred that the object of Domestic Violence Act, 2005 is in POSH Act, 2013, and vide this interpretation only it has expanded the scope of perpetrators in the Domestic Violence Act. It can be conferred through the observations of the Bench that, a law which is trying to classify a section of society and vest some rights in it, such a classification will not be reasonable, if other laws with similar intent is providing that right and relief to other sections of society as well, and UGC Sexual Harassment and POSH Act, do fall on the same objective of abolishing acts of sexual harassment.

Law and society develop gradually, where sometimes either law leads to advancement of society, or the progressive society influence the law making for the concerns on which the law is silent. It is evident that there are many issues on which sometimes the domestic law is silent, however, the international conventions and treaties has dealt with. Sexual harassment at workplace was one such issue which was not dealt by any domestic law when the landmark case of Vishakha NGO was being dealt on by the Supreme Court. The three-judge bench took recourse to international treaties and conventions like CEDAW,[20] to expand the meaning of rights conferred by this constitution, and conferred that humiliation because of sexual harassment is violation of right to live with dignity. Through the aid of Article 51(c), 73, 253 and Entry 14 of the Union List, the bench inferred that "sexual harassment at workplace" is a grave violation of Article 14, 19, 21 and specifically 19(1)(g), as such act disturbs a person's right to

profess in a healthy environment. It is pertinent to notice that, the bench has inferred in the para 10 that, sexual harassment at workplace is a violation of Human Rights in general, it's just that the issue in the judgment pertains to protection of rights of women who are considered as vulnerable, that the bench, in general, dedicated the judgement and guidelines for women.

Since, the Supreme Court has recognised workplace sexual harassment as contravening the Human Rights, so it would not be wrong to confer that any person, irrespective of the gender or sexuality, can approach the Human Rights Commission (State or National) with the grievance of sexual harassment. However, it is a sad state of affair that Human Rights Commission in India holds just the investigative powers and no redressal can be granted by it, which can be inferred from a bare reading of its functions stated under section 12 of the Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993. Therefore, the only effective recourse left with the heterosexual males and the citizens from the LGBTQIA community is to approach the Courts of records with the writ of mandamus for recognition of conventions like that prescribed by the International Labour Organizations, ICCPR, etc. The 190th Convention of ILA, which is still not ratified by India discusses about the importance of abolition of sexual harassment acts against employees, without any discrimination of any kind. However, since India has not ratified the convention till now, the recourse left with LGBTQIA employees is in a very ambiguous state.

Promoting Inclusion: Eliminating LGBT Discrimination and its Positive Impact on Company's Growth

Assessment of Current Workplace Discrimination

Discrimination at the workplace is the most crucial factor when it comes to its impact over the productivity of the Company. According to "96th Session of the International Labour Conference" that discrimination at workplace leads to violation of human rights which tends to lower the human potential and it adversely affect the productivity and economic development. Basically, discrimination is a barrier to poverty reduction as well as it increases socio-economic inequalities. It is very important to evade the discrimination on "LGBT AND Non-LGBT" employees for a better society as well as fostering economic growth[21]. In one of the global reports of ILO it was quoted that "be it any kind of working organization or a workplace it was a strategic entry point to be free from discrimination"[22]. According to "the world bank report of sets LGBTI Inclusion Index" following are the dimensions which can include LGBTI:

According to the above figure the purpose of considering this community under these demands is to get them equipped with the community in a better manner. It was revealed by the study of UN that out of 197 countries there are only 67 countries who implemented measures to prohibit workplace discrimination based on sexual orientation[23].

It was mentioned in one of the article of the "Economic Times" by Rashmi Vikram who is a senior manager at community business which is a not-for-profit organization stated about the 2018 survey of "Times Job" regarding the General attitude of workplace towards the LGBTQ+ which provided by 57% of candidates that their companies did not recruited openly the LGBTQ+ individuals and additionally more than 55% reported that they were treated with biasness for the issues related to "homosexuality and cisgender"[24].

LGBT workers often resort to downplay their identity at their workplace to save themselves from the disadvantage which leads to emotional and cognitive cost. However, these tactics won't work because it cannot hide himself from informal interaction which may lead to their status visible to their co-workers by their gestures and make a "Heterosexist and Trans phobic" comments alike by their own assumptions that their peer are heterosexual or cisgender[25]. Directly or indirectly in the matter of sexuality of the employee even if he or she hides their identity can cause an emotional impact to the employee and also impact in the company's productivity. It was analysed in one of the projects of international labour Organization that because of the fear many LGBT employees tend to hide their sexual orientation and when asked about personal life they tend to hide or alter their partners and they are totally refrained about telling their personal work life[26].

Decriminalization of the rights of LGBT community leads to the protection of their rights via legislation but Decriminalization of the rights of LGBT community leads to the protection of their rights via legislation but the the factors of discrimination are identified in the informal manner and not the formal manner because of the stereotypical cultural behavior of the staff present in the workplace[27].

The International labour organization also discusses the problems in the working environment for the community which are provided under the figure below:

Source: fig 2[28]

Recognizing and addressing the potential problems related to "work-environment cycle" is important to make an organization inclusive of the community from the time of recruitment to termination of employment. It has become very important to implement the policies that promote "Equality among the diverse community". All this will be inclusive of the on-boarding mentorship programs and addressing discrimination issues which ensures that the cycle for the work runs smoothly. There was advice made in the chapter 3 Access to labour market of "world bank" report on sexual orientation and gender identity to "Establish a legal framework which allows the victims of the sexual orientation victims related to employment discrimination to report the cases in public and private sectors and pursue available remedies"[29].

Strategies for Creating Inclusive Work Environment

As previously discussed, the data of 55% of workers who were part of the community reported that they are treated with biases and it is stated further that most of the members tend to hide their orientation or transness which leads to a factor of social anxiety among them. The presence of legislation or the provision may not be sufficient to protect the community or help them to open up themselves at the workplace and also there is a need to expand the provisions with regard to policies of the company and the ideology of the policies behind.

As per the EQOSOGI report of world bank on equal opportunity for sexual gender and minorities, chapter three indicates the access to identify the "national laws, constitutional provisions and regulations" that prohibits discrimination on the basis of sexual orientation. According to Article 7 of ICESCR, the workplace includes the right to be free from physical and mental harassment, which includes sexual and mental harassment in both the private and public sector. It is the fundamental responsibility of a government to promptly enact the effective legal measures to protect individuals from sexual harassment[30]. This also includes the imposing of criminal penalties and establishing a clear definition of sexual harassment applicable to both public and private domains.

To begin with there is a legislation present in the UK that is "Employment Equality (Sexual Orientation) Regulation, 2003" prohibits the "employers unreasonably discriminating against the employees on the grounds of sexual orientation, perceived sexual orientation, religion or belief and age." Further the "Employment and Non-Discrimination Act, 2009" of United provides a nationwide prohibition of discrimination against employment based on orientation. One of the most effective strengths of these legislation is a proactive approach towards the organization but it is still avoiding the provisions which can refrain the non-LGBT employees from criticizing the LGBT employees.

In Argentina there are the provisions related to Anti-discrimination agreements related to sexual discrimination and orientation and gender identity[31]. Encouraging such policies and making it as a compulsion via legislation can create a safer and employment-friendly environment at work culture and it can lead to better employee-contribution with better ideas in an organization. The Rule 5A Ontario human rights commission comes up with the anti-harassment and anti-discrimination policies which have considered that workplaces must have separate policies for harassment and other obligations[32].

In India the top companies have come up with the "Equal opportunity and Anti-discrimination policies." with reference to transgender policies in India Tata Consultancy service is one of the topmost company who promotes "Gender diversity which expands the term fostering the discussion with inclusion"[33] Further the startups like Zomato has come up with the policy which will allow transgender employees to use 10 menstrual leaves a year[34]. Companies like tata and Zomato have brought up many anti-discrimination policies but there is a need and a requirement to provide a legal protection for LGBTQ for example how there was inclusion of other groups like women and the lower casts. According to ILO the legal norms will forbid a social security discrimination and these laws will safeguard the community from discrimination in relation to the individuals of the community[35].

End Results:

Inclusion of LGBT can create long-term benefits of the employer as well as the organization. There was a reference of dimension of the LGBTQ in the above-mentioned

topic with respect to what will the consequences in long term if there is no proper recognition given to the community for the same the international labour organization have stated the results if the LGBT will be recognised and the following have been recognised:

Source Fig3[36]

The above picture recognizes that when the proper education is provided to the community then there will be an only criterion for the workplace that is the competence of the person. If an individual is well educated then there is no requirement for the community to judge on any other basis. The inclusive work culture can be only considered when a company selects on the basis of competency and makes them leave with respect, which can be the only manner where a company can be productive.

The study has been conducted by one of the groups of Infosys by "IGLU" that is Infosys Gay Lesbian Employees and You which focuses on creating a more inclusive and diverse workspace environment at Infosys. Where it was recognized by the company was a connection between employees' sexuality and workplace productivity[37]. Infosys analysed that all the employees including those of LGBT community should be solely based on their ability to work. The company has acknowledged the fact that an inclusive work culture is beneficial for both the community as well as the organization.

The above-mentioned facts state that Infosys is setting an example for other organizations to follow, fostering an environment where every person irrespective of their identity can contribute to the company. Such contributions not only make a better workplace but give a different position to companies as leaders in the world where diversity and inclusion are the central to success.

Conclusion

The research study has led to the finding that, Indian laws still being stereotypical in nature, are not enough to support and improve the plight of LGBTQIA community in the employment sector. This can be conferred from the fact of reluctance on part of the government to recognize them as SEBCs and grant them reservations. The Transgender's Protection Act, 2019 also doesn't makes any punitive measure that can be taken against an establisher if, they discriminate against any person on the account of them being a transgender. The biggest vacancy in law is that, the community doesn't have any recourse to take if they suffer sexual harassment and humiliation at the workplace.

The research has also dealt upon the situations where it represented the data of world bank and ILO where it has shown that even after providing the benefits of protection the community are still discriminated against at workplaces. The ICESR includes the right to be free from physical and mental harassment and makes it compulsory for the state to enact the legislation which can protect the community from the harassment by addressing this ICESR recognizes the laws and raise awareness about the consequence of harassment and promoting culture of respect within community. The research has further gone through how countries like Argentina has provided legislation for the Anti-discrimination policies and ensured the rights and opportunity which fosters the change in among the diversity. Such culture not only protects individuals from harassment but reduces the cost stigma and contribute more towards the society. Lastly, the research was ended by expanding the results that if such kind of discrimination is stopped by the means and mechanisms of the policy and legislation there will be a better result from both the side that is the welfare of the employees as well as the organizational growth.

Therefore, the Hypothesis stands disproved as personal autonomy is not enough and the legislators need to expand the scope of welfare laws of the LGBTQIA community with respect to just regulation and administration in employment sector.

SUGGESTIONS: The Indian psychology works on the idea of orientation as a matter of personal interface, which need not be discussed outside the four walls of one's personal space. However, the companies should do away with such policies allow a place for expression and expansion so that, the people of this community as a whole don't feel self-reproachful about their inherent feelings and are able to work more inclusively, which will help all the employees to increase their level of tolerance as well.

The employment sector and the companies specifically, should take inspiration from Infosys, who have constructed an LGBT employees network known as IGLU (Infosys Gay Lesbian Employees and You) which conducts and promotes activities like discussions and events that aims at spreading the idea of tolerance and diversity in working culture. The Companies should also frame policies against discrimination, humiliation and harassment specifically for the community, as this would give them a sense of recognition.

P: ISSN No. 2231-0045
E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438

VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Periodic Research

The only way to curb the discrimination against LGBTQIA is to either amend laws to gender neutral, and more from a Human Rights Perspective than women centric. Most of the third gender population have a very informal and non-uniform source of income, and hence, their economic status is weak. Therefore, the state of India should work on shifting its focus from caste based to economic status-based reservation as per 103rd Constitutional Amendment,[38] so that the people who really need the substantive equality can have access to it.

Finally, it is crucial, relevant and an essential for the primary education system in India to include in its curriculum, topics related to Sex education, Sexuality and Gender, so that the future generations don't do the mistake that we have done or suffered through. It is important to each and every one to understand the meaning of and what comprises of LGBTQIA.[39]

References

Cases:

1. *Chinder Pal Singh v. The Chief Secretary and Ors.*, 2023 SCC OnLine Raj 907.
2. *Bostock v. Clayton County, Georgia*, 2020 SCC OnLine US SC 2.
3. *Dr. Malbika Bhattacharjee v. ICC*, W.P.A. 9141 of 2020.
4. *Nangai v. The Superintendent of Police, Karur District*, 2014 (3) CTC 497.
5. *National Legal Service Authority v. Union of India*, 2014 5 SCC 438.
6. *Navtej Singh Johar v. Union of India*, AIR 2018 SC 4321.
7. *S. Sushma and Anr. v. Commissioner of Police, Chennai and Ors.*, (2021) 5 MLJ 9.
8. *V. Vasanta Mogli v. State of Telangana*, 2023 SCC OnLine TS 1688.
9. *Vishakha v. State of Rajasthan*, (1997) 6 SCC 241.

Articles/Journals:

1. 96th Session International Labour Conference Report, "Equality at work: Tackling the challenges" (pp. 1), ISBN- 978-92-2-118130.
2. Badgett M.V. Lee and Sell Randell, 2018, "A set of Proposed Indicators for LGBTI Inclusion Index", United Nation Development Programme, "<https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/608921536847788293/pdf/129913-WP-UNDP-Indicators-for-the-LGBT-IInclusion-Index.pdf>"
3. Ramesh Rashmi and Sabharwal Nishtha, 2018 November 24, "India Inc is not creating inclusive workplace for LGBT employees", <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/politics-and-nation/india-inc-is-not-creating-inclusive-workplace-for-lgbt-employees-people-with-disabilities/articleshow/66778071.cms?from=mdr>
4. Cech, E.A., and Rothwell, W.R. (2020). LGBT Workplace Inequality in Federal Workforce: Intersectional Process, Organizational Context and Turnover Consideration, *ILR Review*, 73(1), 25-60. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0019793919843508>
5. *Discrimination on the basis of sexual orientation and gender identity: Results of the ILO'S PRIDE Project*. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---gender/documents/briefingnote/wcms_368962.pdf
6. "Living with Sexual Dignity Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity- Based Human Rights Violation in Housing, Work and Public Spaces in India", Anon (2019), <https://icj2.wpenginepowered.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/India-Living-with-dignity-Publications-Reports-thematic-report-2019-ENG.pdf>
7. *Sexual Orientation*, Ontario Human Rights Commission (2008), https://www.ohrc.on.ca/en/code_grounds/sexual_orientation
8. Tata Consultancy Service, August 2021, "Inclusion Without Exception", TCS, <https://www.tcs.com/who-we-are/diversity-equity-inclusion/dei-framework-neurodiversity-gender-race>
9. Zomato, August 2020, "Zomato Guidelines and Policies", Guidelines and Policies | Zomato
10. "Inclusion of lesbian, gay, Bisexual, transgender, intersex and queer (LGBTQ+) persons in the world of work: A learning guide", ISBN- 978-92-2-036726
11. "Globalization of Professional Services", ISBN: 978-3-642-29180-7
12. K. Jayana, TRANS EQUALITY IN INDIA: AFFIRMATION OF THE RIGHT TO SELF-DETERMINATION OF GENDER, 13 NUJS L. Rev. 3 (2020), ISSN L: 0975-0207
13. A.C. Erin and R.R. William, LGBT Inequality in the Federal Workforce: Intersectional Processes, Organizational Contexts, And Turnover Consideration, *ILR Review*, 73(1), January 2020, pp. 25-60

Laws & Statutes:

1. *Constitution of India*, 1950, Article 14, 19(1)(g), 21.
2. *Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act*, 2019

P: ISSN No. 2231-0045
E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438

VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Periodic Research

3. *The Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013*
4. *International Labour Organization,*
5. *C100- Equal Remuneration Convention, 1951 (No. 100)*
6. *C190- Violence and Harassment Convention, 2019*
7. *Employment Equality (Sexual Orientation) Regulation, 2003 (United Kingdom)*
8. *Employment and Non-discrimination Act, 2009 (United States)*
9. *International Convention on Economic, Social and Convention Rights, 1976*

Database:

1. *J. Store*
2. *Lexis Nexis*
3. *Manu Patra*
4. *SAGE*
5. *Supreme Court Cases*

Endnote

1. *Bostock v. Clayton County, Georgia, 2020 SCC OnLine US SC 2.*
2. *Chinder Pal Singh v. The Chief Secretary and Ors., 2023 SCC OnLine Raj 907*
3. *National Legal Service Authority v. Union of India, 2014 5 SCC 438*
4. *Nangai v. The Superintendent of Police, Karur District, 2014 (3) CTC 497*
5. *V. Vasanta Mogli v. State of Telangana, 2023 SCC OnLine TS 1688*
6. *K. Jayana, TRANS EQUALITY IN INDIA: AFFIRMATION OF THE RIGHT TO SELF- DETERMINATION OF GENDER, 13 NUJS L. Rev. 3 (2020)*
7. *Badgett M.V. Lee and Sell Randell, 2018, "A set of Proposed Indicators for LGBTI Inclusion Index", United Nation Development Programme, "https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/608921536847788293/pdf/129913-WP- UNDP-Indicators-for-the-LGBT-IInclusion-Index.pdf"*
8. *A.C. Erin and R.R. William, LGBT Inequality in The Federal Workforce: Intersectional Processes, Organizational Contexts, And Turnover Consideration, ILR Review, 73(1), January 2020, pp. 25-60*
9. *Act 25 of 1976 amended by Act 49 of 1987.*
10. *The Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013, ACT NO. 14 OF 2013.*
11. *Act No. 53 of 1961.*
12. *Supra note 3, Para 80.*
13. *Act No. 40 of 2019, enacted on 5th December, 2019.*
14. *C100 - Equal Remuneration Convention, 1951 (No. 100).*
15. *Mathews A.B., and Singh Samarth, (2021), Queers in Combat: Analyzing the Indian Armed Forces' LGBT Exclusionary Policy, 5.1 CALQ (2021) 41, Pg. 59.,*
16. *Navtej Singh Johar v. Union of India, AIR 2018 SC 4321.*
17. *Bill No. XLIX of 2014.*
18. *Supra note No. 6, Pg. No. 2.*
19. *Dr. Malbika Bhattacharjee v. ICC, W.P.A. 9141 of 2020.*
20. *Convention on the Elimination of all forms of Discrimination against women, New York, 3rd September, 1981.*
21. *Part 1, Defining and Measuring Discrimination, 96th Session "International Labour Conference Report, Equality at work: Tackling the challenges (pp. 22-23)"*
22. *Introduction, 96th Session "International Labour Conference Report, Equality at work: Tackling the challenges" (pp. 1), ISBN- 978-92-2-118130.*
23. *Supra Note 21*
24. *Ramesh Rashmi and Sabharwal Nishtha, 2018 November 24, "India Inc is not creating inclusive workplace for LGBT employees", https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/politics-and-nation/india-inc-is-not-creating-inclusive-workplace-for-lgbt-employees-people-with-disabilities/articleshow/66778071.cms?from=mdr*
25. *Cech, E.A., and Rothwell, W.R. (2020). LGBT Workplace Inequality in Federal Workforce: Intersectional Process, Organizational Context and Turnover Consideration, ILR Review, 73(1), 25-60.*
26. *Discrimination on the basis of sexual orientation and gender identity: Results of the ILO'S PRIDE Project. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---gender/documents/briefingnote/wcms_368962.pdf*
27. *Part 3, Institutions and Policies: Trends, Impacts and Challenges, 96th Session International Labour Conference Report, "Equality at work: Tackling the challenges" (pp. 56), ISBN- 978-92-2-118130.*
28. *Supra Note 25*
29. *Supra Note 23*
30. *"Living with Sexual Dignity Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity- Based Human*

P: ISSN No. 2231-0045**RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438****VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025****E: ISSN No. 2349-9435****Periodic Research**

Rights Violation in Housing, Work and Public Spaces in India”, Anon (2019)

31. Supra Note 27

32. Sexual Orientation, Ontario Human Rights Commission (2008),

33. Tata Consultancy Service, August 2021, “Inclusion Without Exception”, TCS, <https://www.tcs.com/who-we-are/diversity-equity-inclusion/dei-framework-neurodiversity-gender-race>

34. Zomato, August 2020, “Zomato Guidelines and Policies”, Guidelines and Policies | Zomato

35. Section A: LGBTQ Person and the World of Work, “Inclusion of lesbian, gay, Bisexual, transgender, intersex and queer (LGBTQ+) persons in the world of work: A learning guide”, ISBN- 978-92-2-036726

36. Supra Note 25

37. Part III: Diversity and Inclusion: A Business Imperative in Global Professional Services, Jain Swati & Lobo Richard (2012), “Globalization of Professional Services”, ISBN: 978-3-642-29180-7